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IMPLEMENTATION OF PRESCHOOL UNIVERSAL EDUCATION IN RURAL PRESCHOOLS OF UKRAINE (1963-1984)

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Emphasis is placed on the periodization of the development of preschool institutions in rural areas of Ukraine in the chronological boundaries of 1945-1991. There are three periods of formation and development of rural preschool institutions: 1st period (1945-1963) refers to the revival and formation of preschool institutions in rural areas, 2nd period (1963-1984) refers to the implementation of preschool education in rural preschools, 3rd period (1984-1991) refers to the renewal of the educational space of preschools in rural areas. The historical facts of the organization of public preschool education in the Ukrainian village in 1963-1984 are generalized – period of dynamic development of rural preschools: intensive construction of preschools in the village according to standard projects, merging nurseries and kindergartens into one institution, mass transformation of seasonal preschools into permanent ones, period of critical analysis, use and implementation of pedagogical experience, scientific and methodological developments, organization of patronage (mentoring) work, creation of "kindergarten schools". The author's periodization is based on scientific achievements in the periodization of the history of pedagogy by socio-economic and political characteristics and periods of formation of Ukrainian statehood. It is emphasized, that periodization is only an author's version, which can be accepted by scientists or refuted by replacing it with another. The following methods were used in the process of scientific research: analysis, generalization, systematization of archival documents, legislative acts, substantiation of the initial positions of scientists and practitioners on the researched problem. Chronological-systemic and historical methods were used in the dynamics and sequence of time to consider the peculiarities of the functioning of preschool institutions in rural areas of Ukraine in the period 1963-1984.

Keywords: preschool institutions, countryside, preschool universal education, preschool upbringing, historical and pedagogical research

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1. Introduction

There is a need to study the peculiarities of the functioning of preschools in rural areas of Ukraine in the past, as it is possible to identify both positive experiences that were once rejected or forgotten, and negative, reprehensible aspects of the process and reaction of contemporaries to their problems, their practical implementation or ignorance.

The analysis of educational policy in a certain historical period leads to reflections on the declared goals, comparison of specific achievements in accordance with the defined goal, justification of the achieved positive results and prevention or avoidance of future mistakes. It should also be guided by the thesis, that the results of educational policy are results with a delay in time, which should and can be assessed, although their social consequences are manifested gradually.

2. Literary review

Ukrainian scholars have noted that one of the important sources of formation of theoretical and methodological foundations of the national system of preschool

education is the results of historical and pedagogical analysis of its origin and development [1], and the probability of reproduction of the pedagogical reality of the past by a historian of pedagogy, the ability to organize a cognitive dialogue between the present and the past allows to comprehend the results [2].

Scholars ask the question: what is the need for the history of education and the history of pedagogical thought in the modern conditions of the establishment of market relations in society? If in Soviet times it aimed to strengthen the ideological resource of science to solve problems of teaching and education, today society expects historians of pedagogy to implement this field of knowledge in practice. They should explain to modern educators: how and why certain models of education were formed; why some of them were effective and others were not; how each model of education of the past is connected with the needs of the society of that time. This will expand the possibilities of forecasting today's educational needs, in particular, to overcome nostalgia for Soviet education. To do this, it is proposed to integrate content and context by focusing not on

doctrines, theories, concepts, but primarily on the problems, to which they are aimed. This will allow to include ideas and texts in the historical context and to consider these ideas as a reaction of a researcher to the challenge of the context, get an understanding of the origin of an idea, understand an idea or text as an event, the results of which are determined by mental process and external circumstances [3, 4].

In the historical and pedagogical scientific works of N. Dichek [5], O. Sukhomlynska [6] we find approaches to the periodization of the history of education/pedagogy by socio-economic, political characteristics, periods of formation of Ukrainian statehood. It is emphasized, that periodization is only an author's version that can be accepted or refuted by scientists. Moreover, an author's periodization is always the result of the scientist's creative activity and reflects the level of his/her professional competence.

There are three periods of the formation and development of rural preschools: I period (1945–1963) – the revival and formation of preschools in rural areas, II period (1963–1984) – the introduction of preschool education in rural preschools, III period (1984–1991) – the renewal of the educational space of preschool institutions in rural areas of Ukraine. The criteria for such periodization were – socio-political, socio-economic, cultural conditions of development of Ukraine in general and rural areas in particular; state regulatory policy; typology of preschool institutions. On the basis of documentary objects the generalization of historical facts of the organization of preschool education in the Ukrainian village of the I period (1945–1963) was carried out – the postwar revival and formation of preschool institutions of the countryside, which led to an idea of association of groups of children of younger and preschool age in one preschool institution [7].

3. Research aim and tasks

The aim of the study is to identify the features of the implementation of preschool "universal education" in rural preschools of Ukraine in the period 1963–1984.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

1. To clarify the concept of "universal education", "preschool universal education".
2. To reveal the conditions of development of different types of preschool institutions in the countryside in the above period, summarizing the historical facts of the organization of preschool upbringing in rural preschool institutions.

4. Materials and methods

In the process of scientific research such general scientific methods as substantiation of initial positions of scientists and practitioners on the research problem were used, as well as analysis and generalization of legislative acts, publications in periodicals, systematization of archival documents to identify ideas, provisions, directly related to the process of practical knowledge of the organization of public preschool education – "universal preschool education" in rural areas of Ukraine in the period from 1963 to 1984. Chronological-systemic and historical methods were used to consider the peculiarities of the functioning of preschool institutions in rural areas

of Ukraine in the dynamics and sequence of time limits of 1963–1984.

5. Research results

Creating the term "universal education" (in Ukrainian "vseobuch") took place in the 50–70s of the last century due to the word bases combination – by connecting the creative bases of each of the words, included in the basic compound. The word-forming affix in this case is the interfix – a morpheme that connects the creative bases. The term "universal education" is given the following definition in explanatory dictionaries – the general compulsory education of school-age children, the widespread promotion of the basics of any knowledge [8, 9]. Under universal preschool education" we will understand the involvement of children of a certain age in the education, upbringing and development in educational institutions, the principle of organization of preschool education.

Preschools have been and remain an important component in the system of non-productive sectors. Subjective (socio-economic) factor in the development of rural preschools in Ukraine is human activity (human factor). Participants in the educational process – heads, educators, music teachers and other employees of rural preschools, the community were the driving force behind the development of these institutions. Not only in accordance with the Law "On strengthening the link between school and life and on the further development of public education in the Ukrainian SSR", adopted in April 1959, but also on their own initiative and conviction, they directed all their strength, skills, desires, enthusiasm and faith in the education of a new human – the builder of communism with a harmonious combination of spiritual wealth, moral purity and physical perfection (as it was propagated at the time).

The socio-economic factor in the development of public preschool education in Ukraine was that the work of such institutions provided the highest productivity of employed women-mothers. If in the conditions of individual maintenance and upbringing of children each child needs a dismissed adult, then in the presence of a preschool institution one person served on average 4 children, and their upbringing was organized at a higher level. However, this was not the end of efficiency. The set of socio-economic indicators proved the expediency and importance of spending on the development of preschool institutions: with the growing number of children, covered by preschool institutions, a positive feature was manifested, the essence of which was the constant increase in the absolute number of women, released from the household. O. Budrin pointed out the economic side of the development of preschool institutions in Ukraine in the article "Socio-economic preconditions of development and scientific bases of placement of preschool institutions" (1967). If we assume, the economist noted, that a mother had only one preschool child (at the beginning of 1966 in the USSR permanent nurseries and nurseries-kindergartens covered about 1.2 million children, the same number of able-bodied women were created conditions in public production. Of this number, about 300 thousand women devoted themselves to the care and upbringing of children in preschool institutions,

and the remaining 900 thousand worked in other sectors of the national economy [10].

The media constantly reported on the continuous growth of a wide network of preschool institutions in Ukraine [11]. Thus, in a speech on the radio on improving children's preschool education in the countryside, Deputy Minister of Education of the USSR I. Khomenko said RATAU correspondent L. Ivanchenkova how constant attention and care a mother, working woman is surrounded by in the country: she was given full opportunity of active participation in the economic and socio-political life of society, as the Soviet state took motherhood and childhood under protection. The Deputy Minister also cited the following statistics: in 1975, there were more than five thousand collective farm preschools in the country, which educated 230 thousand pupils [11]. Where necessary, in the midst of field work, seasonal nurseries were established, covering more than 500,000 children. Much has been done to further improve and develop rural preschools in the current five-year plan period: the construction of preschools at the expense of collective and state farms, as well as rural enterprises. This case was best delivered in Dnipropetrovsk, Kirovohrad, Crimea, Mykolaiv, Cherkasy regions [11]. Rural kindergartens and nurseries were built, as a rule, accord-

ing to typical projects in picturesque places. Such a technique as opening of the plane of the main facade in the direction of landscapes solved many educational problems. Extensive use of local conditions (forest, orchards, fields, lush meadows) contributed to the formation of rural preschoolers' cognitive interests, while observing the beauty of the surrounding nature with its rich flora and fauna. Most of their buildings with adjacent sports and playgrounds have been arranged similar to those, built in cities. Every year Ukoopspilka contributed hundreds of millions of rubles to the purchase of children's furniture, toys and pedagogical literature. The Ministry of Education of the Ukrainian SSR together with the republican ministries of trade, light, local industry, Ukoopspilka systematically held competitions to create the best models of new games and toys [11]. More than forty items were proposed for introduction into production only as a result of a competition, held in 1974 [11].

However, the nurseries, which were supported by the budget of the health care authorities of the Ukrainian SSR, were not in the best condition. From the report on their material and technical base on the example of Sumy region (1972) we conclude that the institutions needed major repairs and improvement of both premises and plots (Fig. 1).

ЕДИНОВРЕМЕННЫЙ ОТЧЕТ
О МАТЕРИАЛЬНО-ТЕХНИЧЕСКОЙ БАЗЕ ДЕТСКИХ ЯСЛЕЙ,
НАХОДЯЩИХСЯ НА БЮДЖЕТЕ ОРГАНОВ ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
ПО СОСТОЯНИЮ НА 1 ИЮНЯ 1972 ГОДА

Республика, АССР, край, область *Сумская*

	Город					Село				
	Всего учреждений	в том числе мощностью				Всего учреждений	в том числе мощностью			
		до 30 мест	30-59 мест	60-100 мест	свыше 100 мест		до 30 мест	30-59 мест	60-100 мест	свыше 100 мест
I. Общее число детских яслей (находящихся в системе органов здравоохранения)	25	7	12	6	-	36	27	9	-	-
II. Характеристика помещений. Число яслей, размещенных:	3	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
— в типовых зданиях . . .	3	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
— в приспособленных с полезной площадью, согласно установленной нормы	6	-	6	-	-	12	7	5	-	-
— в приспособленных с полезной площадью ниже установленной нормы:	16	6	4	6	-	24	20	4	-	-
в т. ч. с полезной площадью на 1 ребенка ниже 1,5 м ²	13	6	2	5	-	10	8	2	-	-
III. Из общего числа детских яслей (строка I)										
а) число помещений, нуждающихся в капитальном ремонте	14	3	7	4	-	12	8	4	-	-
б) аварийных помещений	4	1	2	1	-	1	1	-	-	-
IV. Благоустройство. Число учреждений, не имеющих:	14	5	8	1	-	35	27	8	-	-
— водопровода	14	5	8	1	-	35	27	8	-	-
— канализации	23	7	11	5	-	36	27	9	-	-
— горячего водоснабжения (центрального)	24	7	11	6	-	36	27	9	-	-
— электрического освещения	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
— веранд	16	5	10	1	-	28	21	7	-	-
— изоляторов	19	6	11	2	-	36	27	9	-	-
— прогулочных площадок	11	3	7	1	-	15	13	2	-	-

Руководитель Центральной районной больницы

20. Июнь 1972 г. *Зав. Сумской облздравотделом*

713 2000
(Б. Кричило)

Fig. 1 Report on the material and technical base of the nurseries of the health authorities of the USSR (State Archives of Sumy region. F. R-3370 op. 1 file 890 sheet 5)

Every year more than two thousand graduates of pedagogical schools and institutes were sent to work in rural kindergartens and nurseries [11]. Educators of children were provided with constant methodological assistance from the departments of public education. Five thousand such employees annually during the month underwent retraining in regional institutes of teacher training and about the same number studied in short-term seminars [11]. Unfortunately, not all farms in the country took due care to keep teachers on the ground. The boards of a number of collective farms did not always provide educators with benefits, enjoyed by pedagogical staff of state preschool institutions, and this led to a turnover of specialists [11]. The outflow of qualified personnel to the city was caused by the untimely commissioning of new buildings (with rare exceptions, it was August–September), and the premises, introduced in November–December, in the winter often remained empty or occupied for economic needs.

Of course, the quality of upbringing and education of preschool children depended crucially on teachers and other employees of kindergartens, but the joint efforts of the village council, the board of the collective farm and the public brought ordinary kindergartens to exemplary support institutions. One of them was the Palad-Komarivsky ungraded kindergarten in the Uzhhorod district of the Zakarpattia region, which during 1978–1988 was the base for all kindergartens with a Hungarian language regime in the district. The kindergarten, which was located in the subdivision of the district department of public education, created truly family conditions for children: it was attended by all preschoolers in the village with almost no passes due to illness, had good physical development, graduates of the kindergarten were satisfied at school. At the suggestion of the village executive committee, the community built a sports ground, a pavilion for outdoor exercise throughout the year, planned to renovate the premises with the completion of a gym and swimming pool. Puppet shows and concerts of school-children were arranged for children in the village House of Culture. Almost all year round, the menu included fresh vegetables and fruits, supplied to the kindergarten by the collective farm. The deputy commission of the village council carefully monitored the quality of products, that the preschool institution was always warm, cozy and joyful [12].

The educational process in rural preschools was carried out according to the same program [13, 14], as in the city, and was aimed at the comprehensive development of young and preschool children. Educators, nannies of nurseries, performing the tasks of the programs, usually made sure that the children grew up healthy, happy, moral and patriotic, loved work. The latter was provided with appropriate educational work with children on homesteads of preschool institutions. And a monthly methodical magazine of the Ministry of Education of the USSR "Preschool education" allocated its pages to heads and educators of preschools in rural areas of Dnipropetrovsk, Zaporozhzhya, Lviv, Kherson, Cherkasy and other regions in order to share experiences of acquainting children with the cultivation of different crops during the season in fields and meadows, orchards and vineyards, machinery and tools, hard and important

work of rural workers, emphasizing the widespread use of observations, excursions and nature walks with preschoolers, taking into account local conditions [15–19].

The village has accumulated considerable experience in raising children and preparing them for school. Special manuals and albums were published to distribute it. Thus, in 1975 a collection "From the experience of collective farm kindergartens" was published, which covered the issues of mastering by preschoolers the program of the native language, the basics of science, the basics of physical education.

Various means were used to promote and disseminate the experience of improving the efficiency of preschool institutions and deepening the content of work with children by public education departments: stands "They have something to learn", organized thematic exhibitions, conferences, and most importantly – educational institutions cared about to form in preschool workers the need to get acquainted with the achievements of the best pedagogical teams, the ability to creatively apply them in their work [20].

During the so-called universal preschool education (author), the work of education departments in identifying and disseminating the best experience of teachers of rural preschools in Ukraine was actualized in a professional edition "Preschool Education" (for the period from 1951 to 1991 Vinnytsia – 2, Volyn – 3, Dnipropetrovsk – 3, Donetsk – 1, Zhytomyr – 2, Transcarpathia – 3, Zaporizhzhia – 5, Ivano–Frankivsk – 2, Kyiv – 8, Kirovohrad – 1, Crimea – 10, Luhansk – 1, Lviv – 3, Mykolaiv – 4, Odessa – 4, Poltava – 6, Rivne – 0, Sumy – 1, Ternopil – 2, Kharkiv – 8, Kherson – 4, Khmelnytsky – 1, Cherkasy – 13, Chernivtsi – 2, Chernihiv – 1 articles of teachers of preschool institutions of rural areas of Ukraine were published in this magazine). In this regard, we would like to note that Cherkasy and Crimean regions were among the leaders in publishing activities on the development of Ukrainian rural preschools.

About 40 years ago, the first publications appeared about the creation of a new educational complex "kindergarten-school" in the villages. In 1983, the magazine "Preschool Education" drew the attention of the general public to the interesting experience of the actual search for possible ways to restructure and modernize the rural ungraded school and the same preschool institution [21–24].

At that time, there were about five thousand ungraded secondary schools in Ukraine [22], which meant that the area of typical premises was not fully used and experienced teachers did not have a sufficient workload. At the same time, according to the Central Statistical Office, more than one and a half thousand farms in rural areas did not have preschools, and a number of ungraded preschools due to weak material base and lack of qualified personnel did not provide an adequate level of educational process [22].

The initiator of the creation of joint institutions "school – kindergarten" in rural areas was Khmelnytsky region [25]. Volodymyr Ilyich Mityuk, director of Tsvitosh Secondary School, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, told the correspondent of the magazine "Preschool Education" about the five-year experience (psychological, pedagogical, social, organizational and financial

principles) of such an institution in the village of Tsvitokha, Slavutych district. According to the teacher, the unity of school and kindergarten contributes to the effectiveness of an integrated approach to the education of preschool children, and the socio-pedagogical significance of the complex "kindergarten-school" he saw in the significant growth of the school's authority since another word was added to its name – kindergarten. The principal was deeply convinced that the school in the village will forever remain an important factor in social development. The number of children in it allows you to safely take responsibility also for preschoolers – your future students. And the rural complexes "kindergarten-school", undoubtedly, contributed to the fulfillment of tasks for the development of social production by mothers [26].

Tsvitok educators were not the only pedagogical team of the republic to create a joint educational institution "kindergarten-school". For example, at the beginning of the new 1983/84 a.y. just in 18 villages of two districts of Khmelnytsky region "schools – kindergartens" were created, where until then there were not even permanent preschool institutions. The region has developed a long-term plan for the establishment of joint institutions "school – kindergarten" in all districts, so that already in the same school year it was planned to cover another 2.5 thousand preschoolers by public education [23].

Cherkasy, Dnipropetrovsk, Zhytomyr, Crimean and Poltava residents went in the direction of creating educational complexes "school – kindergarten". Not everything turned out as planned, there were problems in solving material, financial and pedagogical issues [22]. However, created in the early 90's of the twentieth century, such institutions are active and promising in the early 20's of the XXI century.

Practitioners have argued in favor of creating "school-kindergarten" complexes, especially in remote rural areas. "We have many small villages where children can be counted on our fingers, there are difficulties with facilities for permanent preschools, but it is necessary to prepare children for school. And on the other hand, there will be, albeit a small one, a kindergarten, united with the school, then the problem of hot meals for students in the ungraded one will be easier to solve, and the school base will be better used", – the headmistress of the Narodytsky District Department of Public Education of Zhytomyr Region, I. Gosteva, shared her thoughts on the importance of new types of educational institutions. The first joint "school-kindergarten" in this district was organized in the village of Motiyka on the basis of a small primary school, where no preschool was established until 1983 [21]. And for three years in 16 districts of Zhytomyr region, taking into account the children's contingent, institutions "school – kindergarten" were created [25, sheet 34].

The Ministry of Education of the Ukrainian SSR positively assessed the organization of joint institutions "school – kindergarten", confirmed the feasibility and prospects of such institutions, especially in rural areas [21, 23]. However, in 1983 the new educational institution "kindergarten-school" due to the lack of regulations

and other normative documents had the status of an informal association [22].

Summarizing the above, we note that the upper limit of the 2nd period (1963–1984) development of rural preschools in Ukraine was determined by the Plenum of the CPSU Central Committee "Main directions of the reform of secondary and vocational schools" (April 10, 1984), whose main goal was radical improving of the whole matter of education and upbringing, preparing the younger generation for life and work [27]. One of the largest reforms in education was announced (in accordance with the resolution of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR "On the main directions of the reform of secondary and vocational schools"), which was determined by social needs. According to the reform of school education, it was envisaged to improve the quality of education and upbringing, raise the public prestige and authority of the teacher, improve his/her theoretical and practical training, and so on. Activities in the form of a social project were planned, which testified to the strengthening of the role of education as a social value.

In fact, the Ukrainian history of education does not exhaust itself. Scientific works of educational historians have made it possible to highlight the relevance of the study of the functioning of rural preschools in Ukraine in the second half of the twentieth century. Focusing research efforts around them, the prospects for further research should be fixed on the problems of introducing preschool education and updating the educational space in rural preschools in Ukraine in the period 1984–1991.

6. Conclusions

Summarizing all the above, we conclude that the identified features of the development of rural preschools in Ukraine in the period from 1963 to 1984 can be described as a process of implementation of preschool "universal education".

1. We use the concept of "universal education" (in Ukrainian *vseobuch*), the formation of which is based on the word bases combination and active use of which dates back to the 50–70s of the last century, in the study as a broad propaganda of the basics of any knowledge. By "preschool universal education" we mean the involvement of children of a certain age in education, upbringing and development in educational institutions, the principles and conditions of the organization of preschool education.

2. Revealing the conditions for the development of different types of preschools in rural areas and summarizing the historical facts of the organization of preschool education in rural preschools of Ukraine in the above period, we conclude that "preschool universal education" 1963–1984 was characterized by intensive construction of preschools on standard projects; there was a mass reorganization of seasonal preschools into permanent ones; there was a specific increase in the number of combined nurseries and the formation of a new type of educational institution "kindergarten school"; deployment of active patronage assistance to rural preschool institutions; using various forms of raising the so-called ideological and political level and

business skills of managers and educators; generalization, introduction of best practices and methodological developments in the practice of preschool institutions.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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References

1. Zaichenko, I. V. (2010). Doshcho pro doslidzhennia problem doshkilnoi osvity v suchasni ukrainskii pedahohichnii nauksi. Istorii osvity. Available at: https://library.udpu.edu.ua/library_files/istoruk_ped_almanax/2010/2010_2_12.pdf
2. Berezivska, L. (2017). Dzherelna osnova istoriko-pedahohichnykh doslidzen yak metodolohichna problema. Suchasni vymohy do orhanizatsii ta provedennia istoriko-pedahohichnykh doslidzen, 6–7.
3. Vakhovskiy, L. (2019). History of Pedagogy as Intellectual History. *Education and Pedagogical Sciences*, 2 (171), 69–76. doi: [http://doi.org/10.12958/2227-2747-2019-2\(171\)-69-76](http://doi.org/10.12958/2227-2747-2019-2(171)-69-76)
4. Hupan, N. M. (2017). History of Education: Crisis and Development. *Ukrainskyi pedahohichnyi zhurnal*, 1, 110–115.
5. Dichuk, N. (2020). (2020) Transformations in the educational policy of Ukraine. *National Identity as a Problem of Science and Education*. Kyiv: Instytut obdarovanykh ditei Natsionalnoi akademii pedahohichnykh nauk Ukrainy, 27–29. Available at: <https://lib.iitta.gov.ua/721116/>
6. Sukhomlynska, O. (2017). Shcho take «istoriia suchasnosti» v istorychnomu vymiri? (komparatyvnyi analiz za materialy zarubizhnykh dzherel). Suchasni vymohy do orhanizatsii ta provedennia istoriko-pedahohichnykh doslidzen, 5–6.
7. Melenets, L. (2021). Research of functioning of rural preschool institutions of Ukraine in the period from 1945 to 1963. *ScienceRise: Pedagogical Education*, 3 (42), 17–21. doi: <http://doi.org/10.15587/2519-4984.2021.232621>
8. Vseobuch – tлумachennia. Available at: <https://goroh.pp.ua/%D0%A2%D0%BB%D1%83%D0%BC%D0%B0%D1%87%D0%B5%D0%BD%D1%8F%D0%B2%D1%81%D0%B5%D0%BE%D0%B1%D1%83%D1%87>
9. Bilodida, I. K. (Ed.) (1970–1980). Vseobuch. Slovnyk ukrainskoi movy. Instytut movoznavstva. Vol. 1. Kyiv: Naukova dumka, 764. Available at: <https://slova.com.ua/word/%D0%B2%D1%81%D0%B5%D0%BE%D0%B1%D1%83%D1%87>
10. Budrin, O. (1967). Sotsialno-ekonomichni peredumovy rozvytku i naukovi osnovy rozmishchennia doshkilnykh dytiachykh zakladiv. *Doshkilne vykhovannia*, 3, 42–43.
11. Visnyk respublikanskoi informatsii (1975). Vol. IV radio – telegrafne ahentstvo Ukrainy pry RM URSR – RATAU, TsAVOV Ukrainy, F. R-5111 Ukrainske informatsiine ahentstvo pry Radi Ministriv URSR (Ukrinform). Kyiv, op. 1, 1943-1991, spr. 1078, ark.463.
12. Siiatska, L. (1973). Systematychno pratsiuvaty z kadramy. *Doshkilne vykhovannia*, 9, 41–44.
13. Prohrama vykhovannia u dytiachomu sadku (1962).
14. Prohrama vykhovannia u dytiachomu sadku (1971).
15. Pertniak, V. Yu. (1970). Vchymo povazhaty pratsiu kolhospyktiv. *Doshkilne vykhovannia*, 7, 27–28.
16. Dotsenko, H. D. (1971). Zbahachennia slovnyka ditei v protsesi oznaiomlennia z pratseiu kolhospyktiv. *Doshkilne vykhovannia*, 5, 28–31.
17. Smyrnova, T. (1975). Formuvannia piznavalnykh interesiv doshkilnyktiv u sposterezhenniakh za pryrodoiu. *Doshkilne vykhovannia*, 6, 29–32.
18. Krutenko, V. (1977). Shana pratsi khliborobskii. *Doshkilne vykhovannia*, 9, 24–25.
19. Kril, M. (1983). Pryvchaiemo trudytysia. *Doshkilne vykhovannia*, 9, 22.
20. Vorobiova, L. P. (1965). Pro kadry kolhospyktiv doshkilnykh zakladiv. *Doshkilne vykhovannia*, 5, 42–43.
21. Hostieva, I. (1983). Pershi sproby. *Doshkilne vykhovannia*, 9, 23.
22. Kroky stanovlennia (1983). *Doshkilne vykhovannia*, 5, 22–23.
23. Leonidova, O. (1983). Zaspiv Khmelnychan. *Doshkilne vykhovannia*, 9, 23.
24. Pered novym startom (1983). *Doshkilne vykhovannia*, 12, 1.
25. Dovidky pro rezultaty perevirky roboty viddiliv narodnoi osvity, shkil, doshkilnykh zakladiv ta pro rozvytok narodnoi osvity (1986). TsAVOV Ukrainy, F. 166 Ministerstva osvity Ukrainy op. 15, 1942–1980, spr. 9291, ark. 151.
26. Melenets, L. I. (2012). Silski doshkilniata i shkoliari pid odnym dakhom: rozдумы z pryvodu nabutoho dosvidu. *Doshkilna i pochatkova osvita: dosiahnennia, problemy, perspektyvy*. Mukachevo, 103–105.
27. Ob osnovnykh napravleniakh reformy obshcheobrazovatelnoi i professionalnoi shkoly (1984). Postanovlenie Verkhovnogo Soveta SSSR 12.04.1984. Available at: <http://www.economics.kiev.ua/download/ZakonySSSR/data02/tex12897.htm>

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